

Ag^I-catalysed oxidation of D-galactose by vanadium(V) in aqueous sulphuric acid solution : A kinetic and mechanistic study^ψ

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Abstract : Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of D-galactose by V^V in aqueous H₂SO₄ solution in presence of Ag^I as catalyst have been investigated. The reaction is first-order each in D-galactose and V^V. The rate of reaction increases on increasing [H⁺] at constant ionic strength due to conversion of unreactive species of V^V to the reactive species of V^V. The sulphate and bisulphate ions shows retarding effect on reaction rate. The inhibitory action of sulphate and bisulphate ions are explained. Silver ion shows positive catalytic effect on reaction rate. The rate of reaction increases on increasing the ionic strength of the medium at constant [H⁺]. The thermodynamic parameters have been computed from the rate constant observed at 35–50°. The fairly high values of negative ΔS[#] and positive ΔH[#] suggest the formation of more ordered activated complex and the transition state is highly solvated. It appears that the rate determining steps involve a slow transformation giving complex. The rate equation has been derived.

Keywords : Kinetics and mechanism, silver(I) catalyst, D-galactose, vanadium(V).

In acid solution vanadium(V) was found to be a powerful oxidant for both organic and inorganic compounds¹. The kinetics of oxidation of cyclohexanone in aqueous sulphuric acid medium is first-order dependent on substrate and hydrogen ion concentration at constant ionic strength². In oxidation of hydrazine and hydroxylamine by vanadium(V), it was observed that 4 mol of vanadium(V) were consumed by one mol of hydrazine and 1 mol of vanadium(V) by 1 mol of hydroxylamine³. General mechanisms for the oxidation of some monosaccharides by vanadium(V) in acid medium has also been reported⁴. The present report is an investigation into the kinetics and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation of D-galactose by vanadium(V) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium in presence of Ag^I catalyst.

Results and discussion

Kinetics of vanadium(V) oxidation were studied at varying concentrations of vanadium(V) in the range (1.0–4.0) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ but at fixed [D-galactose], [H⁺], [Ag⁺], ionic strength and temperature of 1.25 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, 1.595 and 313 K respectively. The average pseudo first-order rate constant (*k*_{obs}) was found to be (2.0007 ± 0.215) × 10⁻² min⁻¹ indicates that the reaction is first-order with respect to vanadium(V).

The order of reaction with respect to D-galactose was determined at different concentrations of D-galactose varying from 2.50 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ to 10.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and at constant [V^V], [H⁺], [Ag⁺], ionic strength and temperature of 3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, 5.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³, 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, 1.559 and 313 K respectively. Plot of log *k* vs log [D-galactose] is linear plot with a slope of unity, indicating first-order in [D-galactose]. From the intercept and slope of the line obtained by plotting 1/*k*_{obs} vs 1/[D-galactose], the rate constant *k* for the slow step and formation constant *K* were calculated. The rate of reaction increases with increasing ionic strength (varied by addition of NaClO₄) of the medium. Sodium sulphate and sodium bisulphate when added under constant ionic strength (NaClO₄ was added to keep the ionic strength constant) showed decrease in the rate (Table 1). The rate of reaction increases as the [Ag⁺] increases. At 3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and 12.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Ag⁺] concentration the catalytic ratios (*k*_{cat}/*k*_o) are 2.8664, 3.0329, 3.5136 and 3.9477 respectively indicate that [Ag⁺] show positive catalytic effect on the reaction rate (Table 1). The rate of the reaction increases with increasing the concentration of H⁺ ion (Fig. 1). The rate of reaction increases with increase in temperature. The enthalpy of activation (Δ*H*[#]) was calculated from the

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Table 1. Effect of added salt and Ag⁺ on reaction rate

[D-Galactose] = 1.25 × 10⁻², [V⁵⁺] = 2.50 × 10⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 5.0 × 10⁻¹, [Ag⁺] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Temp 40°

[Na ₂ SO ₄] × 10 ² , mol dm ⁻³	0	0.05	0.075	0.10	0.125
[NaClO ₄] × 10 ² , mol dm ⁻³	0.375	0.225	0.150	0.075	0
k × 10 ³ , min	24.24 ± 0.754	19.99 ± 0.931	15.32 ± 0.653	12.38 ± 0.959	10.2593 ± 0.761
[NaHSO ₄] × 10 ² , mol dm ⁻³	0	6.0	12.0	18.0	24.0
[NaClO ₄] × 10 ² , mol dm ⁻³	24.0	18.0	12.0	6.0	0
k × 10 ² , min ⁻¹	2.084 ± 0.119	1.52 ± 0.083	1.438 ± 0.085	1.17 ± 0.106	1.094 ± 0.0483
[V ⁵⁺] = 3.0 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³					
[Ag ⁺] × 10 ³ , mol dm ⁻³	0	3.0	6.0	9.0	12.0
k × 10 ³ , min ⁻¹	2.4387 ± 0.3972	6.9902 ± 0.6814	7.3962 ± 0.499	8.7149 ± 0.5047	9.6272 ± 0.9766
k _{cat} /k _o	-	2.8664	3.0328	3.5736	3.9477

Fig. 1. Plot of k_{obs} vs $1/[H_2SO_4]$ at 40 °C. [D-Galactose] = 1.25 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [V⁵⁺] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Ag⁺] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³.

slope of the plot of $\log\left(\frac{k_{obs}}{T}\right)$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 2). The values of ΔH^\ddagger , E_a , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are calculated as 87.36 ± 0.45 kJ mol⁻¹, 92.49 ± 0.46 kJ mol⁻¹, -30.22 ± 0.01

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log\left(\frac{k_{obs}}{T}\right)$ vs $1/T$. [D-Galactose] = 1.25 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [V⁵⁺] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Ag⁺] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³.

JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and 96.68 ± 3.53 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The fairly high value of negative ΔS^\ddagger suggests the formation of more ordered activated complex and transition state is highly solvated.

Mechanism :

The following mechanism is proposed on the basis of results,

(D-Galactose)

Radical

(Radical)

(Complex)

Complex

where R is carbohydrate chain and S represents D-galactose. The rate law from the above mechanism could be written as :

$$\frac{-d[V^{5+}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[S][V^{5+}][Ag^+]}{1 + K} \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) could also be written as

$$\frac{-2.303 d \log [V^{5+}]}{dt} = k_{obs} = \frac{kK[S][Ag^+]}{1 + K} \quad (2)$$

By taking reciprocals of eq. (2)

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{kK[S][\text{Ag}^+]} + \frac{1}{k[S][\text{Ag}^+]} \quad (3)$$

A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{D-galactose}]$, at constant V^V was linear with a small intercept on the y-axis, offering kinetic support for complex formation.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions of V^V were prepared in double-distilled water by dissolving appropriate amount of ammonium metavanadate and sulphate acid. Stock solutions D-galactose, potassium bisulphate, potassium sulphate were prepared in double-distilled water. V^V solution was standardized by redox titration⁶. The rate of the reaction was followed by quenching an aliquot of the reaction mixture in a measured excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate and back titrating the unreacted Fe^{2+} against standard dichromate using *N*-phenyl anthranilic acid as the indicator.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by keeping reaction mixture containing excess of V^V until the reaction was completed and then determining the unreacted V^V . The stoichiometry thus determined was found to be 16 mol of V^V to 1 mol of D-galactose.

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